

VISUALIZING THE SOLAR SYSTEM USING PYTHON AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: We all know that in today's globalized modern world, providing quality education to students is one of the urgent tasks of today's education system. In particular, young people's mastery of foreign languages, computer technologies, web programming, and graphic design will have a positive impact on the future of our society. This article details how to create a model of the solar system using Python's graphical capabilities. This practice increases students' interest in graphic programming, and by imagining the planets, students' interest and outlook on space science expands. Effective results can be achieved by using this experience in astronomy classes.

Key words: Python, Turtle library, Solar System, Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, Neptune

I. INTRODUCTION

Providing students with textbooks suitable for their intellectual potential is one of the important issues of today. [1, 2]. The creation of terminological dictionaries for programming

languages makes it easier for students to master them [3]. But today there are many different programming languages, and the Python programming language is taught in the 9th grade of a general education school. Most students are not interested in programming, so it is desirable to conduct simple and interesting practical experiments to arouse their interest in the field of programming. One such interesting experiment is the visualization of the solar system. It would be so fun if we could see how a solar system actually looks in space. Infact, why not try and make a visual depiction of a Solar System using Python? In this paper, we are going to develop a visual of our Solar System using Python. What is a Solar System?

There are eight planets in the solar system [6]: Mercury, Venus, Earth, Mars, Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune. The four inner solar system planets : *Mercury, Venus, Earth, and Mars* fall under the category of *terrestrial planets*; Jupiter and Saturn are *gas giants*- giant plants composed mostly of hydrogen and helium while Uranus and Neptune are the *ice giants* –containing mainly elements heavier than hydrogen and helium. Pluto, a dwarf planet, was classified as one of the solar system planets when it was first discovered by Clyde Tombaugh. However, it is now considered to be one of the largest known members of the Kuiper Belt — a collection of icy bodies on the outer fringes of the solar system. Pluto was demoted from its planetary status in 2006 when a body of scientists decided a formalized definition for the term “planet.”

According to the International Astronomical Union's definition, a planet is “a celestial body that (a) is in orbit around the Sun, (b) has sufficient mass for its self-gravity to overcome rigid body forces so that it assumes a hydrostatic equilibrium (nearly round) shape, and (c) has cleared the neighborhood around its orbit.” Because Pluto is part of the Kuiper Belt, and therefore has not met the third criterion, it is no longer considered a planet. Instead, it is classified as a dwarf planet. Other dwarf planets include Ceres, Haumea, Makemake, and Eris.

With an atmosphere, stark surface features, and at least five moons, Pluto is

the most complex dwarf planet we know, and one of the most surprising solar system planets. New Horizons flew by our favorite dwarf planet in July 2015 and scientists continue to uncover surprising details about this faraway world.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1. *Getting started with the Turtle library*

Python is a high-level interpreted object-oriented programming language with dynamic semantics. Python can be widely used not only in the field of NLP, but also in working with graphical objects [9]. Turtle Graphics is a popular way to introduce students to Python-based programming. It was part of the original Logo programming language developed in 1967 by Wally Furzeig, Seymour Papert and Cynthia Solomon. The turtle module provides turtle graphical primitives in both an object-oriented and procedural fashion. Because it uses Tkinter for the underlying graphics, it needs a version of Python with Tk support installed.

Turtle programming. The first thing you'll learn when you start programming with the Python Turtle library is how to get the turtle to move in the desired direction. You will then learn to adapt the turtle and its environment. At the end, you will learn some additional commands that you can use to perform some special tasks.

Moving the Turtle

There are four directions that a turtle can move in:

- Forward
- Backward
- Left
- Right

The turtle moves `.forward()` or `.backward()` in the direction that it's facing. You can change this direction by turning it `.left()` or `.right()` by a certain degree. You can try each of these commands like so:


```
Python >>> t.right(90)
>>> t.forward(100)
>>> t.left(90)
>>> t.backward(100)
```

When you run these commands, the turtle will turn right by ninety degrees, go forward by a hundred units, turn left by ninety degrees, and move backward by a hundred units. You can see how this looks in the fig.1 You can use the shortened versions of these commands as well:

- **t.rt()** instead of t.right()
- **t.fd()** instead of t.forward()
- **t.lt()** instead of t.left()
- **t.bk()** instead of t.backward()

Figure.1

You can also draw a line from your current position to any other arbitrary position on the screen. This is done with the help of coordinates(fig.2)

Figure 2.

The screen is divided into four quadrants. The point where the turtle is initially positioned at the beginning of your program is (0,0). This is called **Home**. To move the turtle to any other area on the screen, you use `.goto()` and enter the following coordinates:

```
>>> t.goto(100,100)
```

Your output will look like this(fig.3) You've drawn a line from your current position to the point (100,100) on the screen.

Drawing a Shape

Now that you know the movements of the turtle, you can move on to making actual shapes. You can start by drawing **polygons** since they all consist of straight lines connected at certain angles. Here's an example that you can try:

Figure 3

```
>>> t.fd(100)
```

```
>>> t.rt(90)
```



```
>>> t.fd(100)
>>> t.rt(90)
>>> t.fd(100)
>>> t.rt(90)
>>> t.fd(100)
```

Your output will look like the following shape (fig 4):

Well done! You've just drawn a square. In this way, the turtle can be programmed to **create different shapes and images**.

Figure 4

Drawing Preset Figures

Suppose you want to draw a circle. If you attempt to draw it in the same way as you drew the square, then it would be extremely tedious, and you'd have to spend a lot of time just for that one shape.

Thankfully, the Python turtle library provides a solution for this. You can use a single command to draw a circle:

```
>>> t.circle(60)
```

You'll get an output like this(fig 5). The number within the brackets is the radius of the circle. You can increase or decrease the size

of the circle by changing the value of its radius.

Figure 5

Changing the Screen Color

By default, turtle always opens up a screen with a white background. However, you can change the **color** of the screen at any time using the following command:


```
>>> turtle.bgcolor("blue")
```

You can replace "blue" with any other color. Try "green" or "red".

You'll get a result like this(fig.6)

Figure 6

Finally we come to the most important part. In this section, we will create a model of the solar system.

2.2 Details of a Python project to create a model of the solar system

In this Python Project, we are going to visualize a Solar System. We will see how the planets revolve around the sun. Also, we will be using different colors to show different planets and assign them with speed and paths to make our project look real. We are going to use the Math Module and Turtle Module to create objects in the solar system and depict their movement.

Project Prerequisites

In this project, we will require basic knowledge of python and its concepts. In this project we will be using two modules:[7]

- Math Module
- Turtle Module

Follow the given steps to visualize the Solar System :

Install the Modules

Import the Modules

Create the GUI Screen

Figure 7.

1. Installing the Modules:

We are going to use the Turtle Module and the Math Module in this paper. Install the modules using the following commands:

pip install turtle

pip install math

2. Importing the Modules:

import turtle

import math

*from math import **

- Turtle Module – This provides us the functionality to create the planets and the sun. We will also make the orbits using the turtle module.
- Math Module – This provides us the functionality to do mathematical operations. We will do many operations to create our solar system.

3. Creating the GUI Screen:

screen = turtle.Screen() – creating the screen

screen.tracer(50)

- *Screen()* – creates a GUI Window.
- *Tracer()* – This traces the path of the turtle visible.

4. Create the Sun:

```
sun = turtle.Turtle()#turtle object for sun
```

```
sun.shape('circle')#shape of sun
```

```
sun.color('yellow')#color of sun
```

- Turtle() – Makes the new turtle object. This object will make the Sun in our Solar System.
- shape() – Defines what shape our Sun will be.
- color() – Defines the color of our Sun.

5. Creating the Planets:

```
class Planet(turtle.Turtle):
```

```
def __init__(self,name,radius, color):#initialize function
```

```
super().__init__(shape='circle')
```

```
self.name = name
```

```
self.radius = radius
```

```
self.c = color
```

```
self.color(self.c)
```

```
self.up()
```

```
self.pd()
```

```
self.angle = 0
```

```
def move(self):
```

```
x = self.radius*cos(self.angle) # Angle in radians
```

```
y = self.radius*sin(self.angle)
```

```
self.goto(sun.xcor()+x,sun.ycor()+y)
```

6. Changing the Angles and Adding the Planets:

```
# making plantes
```

```
mercury = Planet("Mercury",40, 'grey')
```

```
venus = Planet("Venus",80, 'orange')
```

```
earth=Planet("Earth",100,'blue')
```



```

mars = Planet("Mars",150, 'red')
jupiter=Planet("Jupiter",180, 'brown')
saturn=Planet("Saturn",230, 'pink')
uranus=Planet("Uranus",250, 'light blue')
neptune=Planet("Neptune",280, 'black')
#adding planets to a list
myList = [ mercury, venus,earth, mars,jupiter,saturn,uranus,neptune]
while True:#while statement
screen.update()#updating the screen
for i in myList:
i.move()#moving the elements of the list
# Increase the angle by 0.0x radians
mercury.angle += 0.05
venus.angle += 0.03
earth.angle += 0.01
mars.angle += 0.007
jupiter.angle += 0.02
saturn.angle += 0.018
uranus.angle += 0.016
neptune.angle += 0.005

```

We make the planets and set them with the attributes. After making the planets we add them to a list.

update() – to update the screen

move() – to move the planets one by one in loop.

Planet.angle – we set the angel of the planets.

Putting all the parts together gives the following set of codes:

Python Solar System Output

Finally, the final result of our practice looks like this:

CONCLUSION:

This article discussed the issue of creating graphical objects in Python. Several practical tasks are covered through simple and interesting practice. Getting students interested in programming is one of the most pressing issues. Because in today's modern era, all processes are being automated. The digital economy is being applied to manufacturing, science, technology and all other fields. So getting students interested in programming from a young age lays the groundwork for their future success. This will certainly have a positive impact on the development of our country.

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